

CLIENTS' SATISFACTION OF ONLINE BANKING SERVICES IN A MUTUAL TRUST BANK IN BANGLADESH

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Abstract

Bangladesh's dynamic, ever-expanding information-driven industry, its online banking sector has flourished, establishing a solid foundation for low-cost banking and an expansion in the usage of mobile devices for financial volume in remote regions. As there is little research on this subject, it is hoped that Online Banking Services (OBS) became a common norm in Bangladesh. This study, titled "The Clients' Satisfaction of Online Banking Services at a Well-Established Bank in Bangladesh," seeks to assess the entire internet banking environment and its effect on customers. It examines the necessity, variables, and limitations of Internet Banking. The objective of this report is to analyse Online Banking Services (OBS) that use these quality-of-service categories to assess the success of OBS and customers' opinions of the value of various parts of OBS. This research can be used by the banking industry's leadership to enhance its customer satisfaction strategy by examining factors that reduce customer problems, facilitate access to treatment, and assure that customers' expectations are constantly met or surpassed. This will result in improved customer interactions and enhancing corporate profitability.

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Since the first email was sent in 1972, the Internet has been one of the most innovative advances in communication. This connectivity enables the ostensibly endless transmission of information throughout the globe (Russett, 2014). There are now new opportunities for individuals and businesses all around the world because of World Wide Web communication (WWW). Because it lowers communication and organization costs while simultaneously improving service delivery and accessibility, this interaction not just binds people while at the same time exposing them to a variety of services and marketplaces, which has resulted in an increase in consumer satisfaction. The ability of businesses to communicate has been greatly boosted as a result of the introduction and growth of the internet. Online Banking (OB) and e-banking is the name given to this internet-based part of banking. Using the Internet as a financial tool in the twenty-first century means being able to do more than just access your account information.

The Automated Teller Machine was the first form of retail electronic banking in Bangladesh (ATM). According to a Central Bank of Bangladesh annual report, online banking has just surpassed its adoption and usage levels (Bangladesh Bank, 2017). This is because rural areas

have a high concentration of low-income residents with easy access to Smartphone's and other mobile devices. Online banking Service Quality (SQ) attributes, such as dependability, security, and privacy, as well as promptness, has an impact on customer satisfaction. This study examines how improved quality of service has enhanced the banking experience for the customer and consequently increased their happiness.

The growth rate of internet banking users shown as follow:

Table 1: Growth Rate of Internet Banking User

Particulars	2014	2015	2016	2017
Growth Rate	27.67%	36.67%	42.36%	98.37%

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Technological growth has resulted in the creation of products and services that have intensified the struggle for market share. Paper-based transactions are being replaced by computerized transactions. Despite the fact that this is a positive benefit, it also raises major challenges for both banks and clients in terms of performance, safety, and economy, among many others. Inside the current period of strong rivalry, many banks have prioritized customer happiness based on the idea that customer-centric firms promote customers' loyalty through enhanced quality of service (Improving customer satisfaction, loyalty, and profit, 2000).

Nevertheless, additional research is required to comprehend the characteristics of online banking that result in customer pleasure, as satisfied customer is a decisive factor to the success implementation of new, innovation, online banking services and their accessibility. The point of the study is to examine the online banking services at a Mutual Trust Bank in Bangladesh, and also the level of client satisfaction.

1.3 Research Questions

- i. Which dimension of service quality should banks consider when measuring the effectiveness of its online banking services?
- ii. In order to quantify the quality for online banking, how are these service-quality parameters used?
- iii. Customers' perceptions of the quality of various components of online banking services are examined in this section.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Online Banking Service

It was in the 1980s that online banking services (OBS), also known as web e banking, developed in the United States. As a means to be more accessible to the general people, several large financial institutions, such as Chase Manhattan and Wells Fargo, began experimenting with "four-wall" internet banking (Krishnan, Online Banking Service, 2014). By utilizing online banking, banks are able to provide customers more features and services, like checking

accounts, purchasing checks, making payments for bills and other obligations, while also saving money on transaction fees. As a result, customers no longer have to travel to a physical location to obtain financial services (Choudhry, 2018). In addition, it saves a lot of money and reduces teller errors, making it a win-win situation. Banking services can now be sold to both developed and underdeveloped countries through OBS. A competitive edge and an economic requirement are met by making banks more accessible to consumers while also enhancing the customer experience (Clemes, 2011).

With the ever-expanding knowledge economy, the banking sector of Bangladesh has experienced a surge in online banking, establishing a solid foundation for low-cost financial services and a rise with the use of cell devices for financial capability, particularly in rural areas. While research on the implications of Online Banking Service (OBS) in the country are scarce, with Munir (MMM, 2015) doing one of the few studies on the phenomenon, OBS is becoming a common norm in Bangladesh. In 2004, Cooperative bank of Bangladesh paved the way for online banking in Bangladesh by allowing users to access their accounts using mobile phones. It provided services such as account balance, SMS alerts for payment card transactions, and alerts for ATM transactions just on account (Alam, 2017).

2.2 Online Banking Service Quality

In customer service, online banking service quality (SQ), also referred to as e quality, is a vital factor. It is also essential to the existence and success of a business. SQ has become a key differentiator in many of the world's leading firms. Main drivers of banking services are enhanced accessibility, reduced costs, improved management, and prediction accuracy (Nupur, 2010). Traditional SQ is described as consumers' attitudes or perceptions of the level of service effectiveness provided by an institution's facilities provided, such as local banks (Herington, 2009).

A gap model for assessing SQ was created by Parasuraman (1988) using the SERVQUAL instrument (Parasuraman, 1988). The attributes of tangibility, reliability, certainty, responsiveness, and sympathy were put to the test in this study. Since then, this instrument has been used in several research to measure SQ (Radhari, 2008). Due to its singular concentration just on service delivery process, this has also drawn a great deal of criticism. Quality of service has several facets, and these facets differ (Santos J. 2003). An integrated data service, Online Banking Service (OBS) has been regarded as a fundamental change in the way businesses engage with their customers. It's difficult to assess the quality of an online banking service because it's not a straightforward one-way transaction. Dimensions such as relevant information, secrecy, and style were created by Ranganathan and Ganapathy (2002). (Ranganathan, 2002). Analysis of an online service tool for evaluating the advantages of internet layout, reliability, fulfilment, customer service and confidentiality and anonymity were among the findings (Gilly, 2003). E-SQ researchers Zeitham, Parasuraman, and Malhotra (2002) conducted research on the following characteristics of web design: aesthetics, ease of navigation and personalization, assurances of privacy and security, reassurances of accessibility and dependability, flexibility and cost-effectiveness. To quantify the dependability and efficacy of an IT system, Parasuraman (2005) developed the E-SQUAL

instrument (Parasuraman, 2005). Additionally, they created E-recSQUAL, which included eleven dimensions based around contact, responsiveness, and compensation. Website interfaces and real-world interactions replaced the variable of tangibles in the study by Li (2009). Web page quality appear to have an impact on customer satisfaction and trust, according to study. In addition, it is widely accepted that web design is more attractive for online shopping and performance expectations are more focused on banking and commercial services. Monitoring client satisfaction has become an essential component of the banking industry as internet banking services have become more widespread (Li, 2009).

2.3 Customer Satisfaction

Because of the multitude of elements that can alter one's mood, contentment is related to a short-lived optimistic attitude. (Hom, 2000) (Hom, 2000). It's useful to look into Bruhn's 2003 statement to see if he was satisfied with the overall efficiency of services (Bruhn, 2003). Customer happiness has been shown to be associated with repeat purchases. Client satisfaction, according to Pairot (2008), is defined as the ability of the company to meet the economic, emotional, or cognitive needs of the customer. He understands that customer satisfaction may fluctuate due to the diverse backgrounds and views of his clients (Pairot, 2008).

Consumers are pleased when their expectations are met or exceeded. It is also a sentiment or attitude established by bank customers after receiving service, which unites their diverse spending patterns (Ahmad Jamal, 2002). Comparing a client's pre-exposure and post-exposure behavioral satisfactions reveals their perception of a company's client satisfaction (Ahmad Jamal, 2002).

Al-Fahim (2013) analyzed the connection between expectancies, competence, and provision of services in a prior study. Clients were found to evaluate items and services by comparing them to a set defined expected performance outcomes. Value or dissatisfaction is recognised in the product's service delivery. The utility, satisfaction, and perceived danger of mobile banking apps were all examined in a separate study by Muneesh Kumar (2013), which focused on customer perceptions of these three variables in relation to their use. The survey discovered that users were receptive to the adoption of mobile payment technologies, but some were offended by the supposed security risk. In a changing and competitive market, consumer happiness has gotten worldwide recognition as a key aspect in corporate strategy when utilising tech (Barbara Culiberg, 2010). This study takes a process-oriented analysis of customer satisfaction since internet banking users help differentiate quality during in the distribution process.

2.4 Online Banking and Customer Satisfaction

Post-purchase satisfaction has become an essential criterion in today's competitive market (Ahmad Jamal, 2002) which must be reached to improve customer relationships since customers are becoming more knowledgeable (Santouridis, 2009). In today's consumer-centric banking environment, a persistent customer-oriented approach is necessary to ensure that excellent execution is consistently being achieved (Ahmad Jamal, 2002). As a result, the bank is able to provide its customers with convenient, quick access to their account information from

any place. Customers are aware of innovations and expect better quality services, which has led to banks constantly improving their online elements (Tilahun, 2016). Non-financial institutions are also in competition with banks, and the argument goes that it is easier to keep and satisfy an existing customer than to try to get a new one (Cohen, 2006). As a result, banks are now required to examine their operations on a regular basis to guarantee that they are meeting the needs of their consumers. Customer satisfaction or dissatisfaction with internet banking depends on a variety of factors.

The subjective assumption is a well-known way of looking at how companies gauge their customers' level of satisfaction (Oliver, 1980). This perspective of view was espoused by Oliver in 1980. Proponents of the "disconfirmation theory" say that customers are happy when a product or service doesn't live up to their expectations in terms of perceived effectiveness. Customer expectations are compared to actual performance of the product they acquire and consume to determine if the expectations are confirmed or refuted, according to this theory. Negative confirmation occurs if Positive confirmation happens when there is a difference between expectations and reality. A measurable measure of happiness or dissatisfaction results (Haddrell, 1996).

For assessing customer satisfaction, productivity scales consist of factors such as outstanding, acceptable, average, and poor. Additionally, there are satisfaction scales with criteria ranging from unsatisfied to satisfied (Haddrell, 1996). They advocate using disconfirmation scales for measuring customer satisfaction since they catch the "SERVQUAL" measurement, which has a two-stage base ranging from far worse than anticipated to much better than anticipated. They also advocate it because a consumer who rates the quality of service as "fair" or "good" may not see it as exceeding their expectations. They determined that a five-point expectations scale is the most accurate way to gauge customer satisfaction based on their examination of other scales with much the same respondents. Client satisfaction is essential for organizations because it provides customer feedback for equipment and technical strategy. This is also true since pleasure is the consequence of firsthand experience with the brand or service, and it arises when perceptions are compared to a benchmark, in this instance, aspirations. (Haddrell, 1996).

2.5 Conceptual Framework

As the key construct, customer happiness or the quality of internet banking service is used to measure the influence of MTBL online service quality on customer satisfaction. According to the published literature, customers' satisfaction is a cumulative notion; thus, this study will examine the online banking services of participants who have been using internet banking over a year.

Customer satisfaction is viewed as the process of evaluating customers when they use Internet Banking Services. This evaluation analyses client expectations and perceptions concerning the quality of online banking service. According to Danaher and Haddrell (1996), an expectations scale is the best suitable for assessing customer satisfaction based on some criteria that comprise internet banking architecture in the distribution process, such as dependability, transaction efficiency, and tech support, among others (Dabholkar, 1996). Following a

comprehensive evaluation of the material, methods, and ideas, the identified research framework was designed:

Figure 1: Conceptual model developed for this study

Safety and dependability are crucial prerequisites for client pleasure. In their research, Parasuraman (1988, 2000) also determined that process predictability, execution of advertising promises, punctuality, and error-free operation constitute reliability. One of its most crucial factors of customer happiness is dependability (Parasuraman, 1988). Service assurance in online banking refers to the providers' efforts to promote a sense of safety and trust. It gives the customer the assurance that his or her permissions and transaction within are secret and protected from hacker and third-party intrusion (Zeithaml, 2002).

Transaction efficiency is measured in terms of the amount of time it takes to get into the system and find the information you need. It also refers to the statement's quality, the time required to acquire a service, and indeed the website's ease of use (Zeithaml, 2002). Through with a customer service centre or a 24-hour chat box, the banks ought to be available to handle or clarify any issues or questions that may arise when consumers utilize the system. The presence of a link mostly on program that offers an instructional explanation of the internet is another method of providing customer service. (Zeithaml, 2002).

Efficiency evaluates the functionality of the website's functionalities. This feature focuses on the usefulness of something like the website rather than its aesthetic appeal. Service content refers to what the organization has supplied on its website; whatever information is available or what was the value? It is crucial for such development of a webpage to have high-quality, simple-to-use information. The web's aesthetic is its design, including how it is packed and displayed. The design must be appealing to attract clients to utilize it.

Table 2: Summary of the Conceptual Model Dimensions

1.Safety and reliability	OBS provides excellent support from the very beginning.
	OBS delivers services It is reported to be able to offer
	OBS performs the tasks precisely.
2.Service and security	OBS maintains precise transaction data.
	OBS ensures that users' data and security are protected.
	Can examine the details of previous transactions at any moment.
3.Transaction efficiency	The information that may be found on OBS is current.
	OBS offers comprehensive support with its help function.
	The transaction process in OBS is lightning-fast.
4.Customer support	OBS provides sufficient details.
	The OBS technique resolves problems rapidly.
	The OBS procedure quickly resolves issues, and the OBS staffs are competent and able to provide guidance about how to use the process effectively.
5.Ease of use	The OBS website is intuitive and simple to use.
	It is simple to locate data and understand instructions on OBS.
	OBS evaluation and monitoring and transaction speed
6.Performance	OBS provides for multi-language
	OBS enables bank transfer
	OBS provides online enrollment
7.Service content	OBS offers reliable information
	OBS gives data that meets criteria.
	OBS offers precise information
8.Site aesthetics	The OBS site is well designed.
	The OBS website is appealing
	The OBS site is well arranged.

3.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Subject of Study

According to the Corporate Law of 1994, a public stock company with a share capital of BDT 200 million and shares worth BDT 100 each was established on September 29, 1999. There are currently rs 10,000,000,000 (BDT 10 billion) in authorized share capital, divided into BDT (one billion) common stock. When 2017 came to a conclusion, Money Tree Bank had 103 locations and 145 ATMs across the country.

On October 5, 1999, the company was granted a license under the Bank Firms Act 1991 by the Financial Institutions and began operating as a bank on October 24th, 1999, after receiving a Certificate of Incorporation. All aspects of commercial banking, including currency exchange and other financial services, are covered by the bank's operations. Customers received customized treatment and the bank grew its clientele on its first 2 years in business.

Individuals and corporations can obtain savings, deposits, payment services, foreign exchange accounts, and loans from the bank. It debuted their internet site in December 2010 and offers

retail and business customers real-time access to their account balances, and also payment processing & interbank take for local and foreign currencies.

3.2 Population of the Study

The population of this study consisted of customer service representatives from Dhaka-based bank branches. They were selected due to their experience and expertise regarding consumer satisfaction. The 2003 Mugenda method was utilized to select a total of 201 participants. This study's major research instrument was a question composed of two substantial parts. The investigation utilized a standardized, self-administered questionnaire to collect information from respondents (Cooper & Schindler 2006; Malhotra & Birks, 2007). For this reason, 201 questionnaires were distributed at randomly to respondents.

3.3 Cronbach's Alpha Test of Reliability

To guarantee that the woman's internal reliability was intact, this method was used. When completing this test, our study grouped various goods based on quality-related elements and carried out the inspection on every dimension. A α -score is a value between 1 to 10 which is used to judge the inherent dependability of each examined variable. A score of 0.7 or higher indicates that the measurement has a better level of internal consistency. (CRONBACH, 1951). The estimated α -scores are presented in Table 3 based on the obtained data.

Table 3: Cronbach's Alpha Scores

Dimension	Ease of use	Performance	System availability	Service security	Safety/ Trust	Site Aesthetic	Transaction	Customer support
Cronbach's Alpha(α -score)	80.1%	77.7%	62%	69%	63.4%	----	61.8%	55.5%

From the table above, it can see that highest α -scores on Performance and usability were rated at 77.7% and 80.1%, respectively. This indicates that the elements relevant to the measurements can be utilized to measure the concept due to the dimensions' high dependability. Privacy-related service security characteristics have a α -score of 69 percent, which is extremely near to 0.70 and is consequently regarded as highly dependable. This is consistent with the results of other study; hence, 0.7 is quite trustworthy.

All of these figures are less than 0.70% of the total. Because only one item is included in dimension, there is no α -score on site aesthetics. Pallant (2005) states that the α -score rises in proportion to the scale's total number of items. That suggests that α -scores or is much less than 0.7 for certain of the features could be the result of fewer questions about those elements (Pallant, 2005). These characteristics having α -scores below 0.70 were included in just two items because of the survey's breadth as well as the time constraints that were placed on the survey implementation. As a result, use of any Cronbach's Alpha Test for Dependability showed that deleting any one of the dimension's given inputs and surpassing 2 questions would not improve the dimension score.

It is vital to note that the survey questions pertaining to the process timeliness and customer service qualities were difficult to understand, resulting in severely low results. 32 questionnaires missed responses to questions pertaining to the payment service provided, while 31 questionnaires missed answers to questions pertaining to customer support, as it was unlikely that the majority of users had had problems with the OBS offered.

3.4 Data Analysis

(PCA) was employed to determine if the division & characterization of a conceptual model's planning of projects were sufficient. Using PCA, numerous components of a original theoretical model was removed and the dimensionality were decreased. PCA resulted in modifications to the baseline model. Consequently, software Statistical Package for social Sciences (SPSS) were utilised to analyse descriptive information, such as percentage and frequency, presented in the form of charts in answer to study questions. For the reader's convenience, a short rundown of principal component follows.

3.4.1 Principal Component Analysis

Data patterns can be discovered through the application of the statistical method known as principal component analysis (PCA). If the approach is used to simplify the initial data, i.e. summarising the original data into a new number of parameters with the least availability of data lost, it shows that the technique is being used to do so. The Principal Component (PC), often known as factors, is variables that explain the most variation in a data set (Li, 2002).

There is a lot of variance in data that can be explained by first principal component, and as much variation as feasible may be described by subsequent components. PCA's adoption is primarily motivated by its ability to reduce the analysis of big datasets and to create new important variables. A set number of customer-answered questions is used in the tests that follow to describe each quality component related to the conceptual model. By employing PCA, researcher was able to identify whether the queries they employed described each quality feature and if some sets of questions originally connected with a given quality dimension might be condensed into fewer features in order to enhance the study's precision.

In order to properly analyse the data, it is necessary to first assess whether the framework created for the research can be used in the banking industry. Factor Analysis of the model's components was performed using PCA, Varimax rotation, and Kaiser Normalization. Outliers were tested to discover if they were present and, if so, how they may affect the data collection process. It is necessary to use KMO and Bartlett's Sphericity in order to determine whether or not the data can be used for Factor Analysis. After determining the host of features (tangible things in this study) that should be kept, Kaiser's criterion was used to exclude items with low applied loads on each category. Detailed findings of the above-mentioned experiments may be found in Appendix V, which also includes a summary of the KMO and Bartlett's Test, the Communalities and Correlation Matrix, as well as the Total Variance Explanation and the component Matrix and Rotated Component Matrix. The data in these tables are described in detail further down the page.

A search for abnormalities was carried out, as previously mentioned. So there were few if any two severe outliers for various queries, they were eliminated from of the data file (Pallant, 2005). For the PCA process, there are still 170 samples to choose from. 0.000 for both the KMO Sampling adequacy & Bartlett's Testing Sphericity and less than 0.05 for the suggestive criterion for Factor Analysis are obtained after the extreme anomalies have been removed. Sampling adequacy is measured by the KMO Bartlett's Test, which returns a result that surpasses the threshold of 0.6 and is appropriate for Principal Component analysis (CRONBACH, 1951). Using PCA as an extract, a Factor Analysis was conducted on 170 cases once the first operations were done, obtaining the results detailed below.

Correlations bigger than 0.3 were identified in the Correlation Matrix, even though the KMO or Bartlett's Tests of Sphericity or Sampling Appropriateness were employed to verify the data's eligibility for Factor Analysis. The extract number of connections for all parameters is sufficient, as can be seen in our table of correlations. Only 39.8 % of Q11 can be explained by all components in the study, which has a communality of 0.398, the lowest of the three factors. As a result, removing this variable from the model is an option. Both Q1 and Q3 share a commonality of 0.428% and 0.457%, respectively.

Variance explained by the proper number of dimensions is shown in the Total Variance Explained column beneath the values in the table. Eigen values are displayed here. When doing PCA, Kaiser's Criterion is utilised as one of the extracts. It is necessary to delete four elements from the dataset in line with Kaiser's criterion, since the number of eigen values greater than 1 indicates the need to do so. There are four elements that account for 59.76 percent of the total diversity in all attributes, whereas there are three factors that account for 54.376 percent, four factors that account for 58.082 percent, and four factors that account for 40.801 percent. Only four variables could be recovered using Kaiser's Criterion and the PCA completed, hence the 20 items need be reorganised into four Seroquel categories.

Because the slope of the graph is pricey only up until the point marked 2 on the horizontal axis, the Screen Plot is yet another technique that can be used to decide which factors must be retrieved. This method showed that only one factor should be extracted in this particular scenario. In spite of this, the research, as was previously mentioned, favoured the utilisation of the Kaiser's Criterion for extraction (which requires that the eigen values be greater than 1), and as a result, four factors will be derived. Based on the information presented above, it can be concluded that the selection of four factors was suitable for this study. Analysing the data that is provided in the Rotated Component Matrix that is located in Appendix V will allow you to determine which method of dividing the variables into four distinct aspects (factors) will be the most efficient.

The Rotated Factor Matrix illustrates the degree of correlation that exists between each variable (row) and the various components (column). As a result, it is important that each variable be assigned to the criterion with which it corresponds the most effectively. In the event that one factor has correlation values that are comparable to those of upwards of one factor, this indicates that this variable can appear to apply equitably well with a variety of factors. As a result, it is presumed that this factor is not very strictly outlined, and as a result, it can be deleted

from the model. Just the correlations those are greater than 0.3 are displayed in the Rotated Component Matrix, which can be found in Appendix V. After looking at the data in the desk, it is clear that the survey questionnaire have the strongest correlation to the very first factor. These questions can be grouped together to show the first factor, which accounts for the biggest proportion of variance in these factors: Question 1 (50.5%), Question 3 (62.5%), and Question 4 (71%) Q5 (60.8%), Question 10 (60.7%), Question 12 (65.9%), Question 13 (62.7%), and Question 14. (59.3 percent). Q1 and Q14 are the only questions that fall under the permissible range of 60% in the Likert scale scenarios for the latent elements. Despite being less than 0.5, the following criteria for Q1 and Q3 were kept in the models. Despite the fact that they'd been first denied, this choice was made. This is because the outcomes of these two investigations are closely linked (plus 50 percent). A similar exposition shows the variables Q6-63%, Q8-51.5%, Q18-58.2%, Q19-82.8 percent, & Q20-58.5 % to be highly correlated, and as such, these numbers should be combined to represent the second component only. With regard to factor loadings, Q6 (plus 60 percent) and Q19 (plus 60 percent) both meet this standard. Questions 18 and 20 are statistically close to reaching a score of 60%, and so, the second element may well be considered to explain them significantly. Even though Q9 is significantly reduced over 60%, coming in at 51.4%, it will be retained because 60 percent is an essentially arbitrary tier for great loading factor in Likert scales situations as well as the increased composite reliability valuation of Q9-57.5 % in this dependent variable that is explained by the model's constructs. In the Likert scales examples, however, 60 percent is an arbitrary threshold for a high coefficient of determination.

The third element should cover the Q7-76.7 percent or Q8-64.5 percent ranges. Both of their Likert Scale factor loadings are above the 60% level, which indicates a high correlation between two variables. There are three ranges that can be used to symbolize the fourth element: 69.2% to 79.9%; 69.2% to 69.9%; and 70.99% to 79% there is a factor loading of + 60% on the Likert Scale for each of these values. As can be seen from the Rotated Factor Matrix, the model is missing two variables which should be taken out. For certain factors, these two variables have nearly identical correlation values, indicating that they are poorly defined. Both the first and third components have correlation coefficients of 59 percent, which indicates that the variable can be explained using both these factors. Q11 has a 40% connection with the first factor, a 37.8% correlation with the second, a 24% correlation with the third, and a 19.3% correlation with the fourth element. These figures show that the correlation between this variable and the first and second factor authentication is virtually perfect, and that the morals are extremely low (less than 50%), meaning that the components can only explain less than half of the variation in the data. In light of the fact that values are below 50%, we can conclude that this is true. The factors will be omitted from the model because of their poor Q11-39.8 percent composite dependability value. That's a reference to the earlier discussion.

The dimensionality contained in the proposed conceptual model must be reduced as a result of this examination of the acquired data. It was found that the basic conceptual model's initial eight dimensions were not adequately clustered, and hence four quality new dimensions needed to be reconstructed from the original eight. We should also include the following factors in the four new quality dimensions:

Quality dimension 1: Q1, Q3, Q4, Q5, Q10, Q12, Q13, and Q14

Quality dimension 2: Q6, Q9, Q18, Q19, and Q20

Quality dimension 3: Q7 and Q8

Quality dimension 4: Q15, Q16, and Q17

In order to create four new quality dimensions, the basic variables have been reorganised almost completely and the dimensions have been renamed. The study named the new dimensions as indicated in Table 3 after evaluating the dimension-variable clusters in Appendix 11.

Table 4: Labels for the Newly Created Dimensions

Items	Question detail	New dimension label
Q1	I am capable to get on the site quickly	Service Performance (Availability, performance, service security, safety)
Q3	The site is constantly accessible for business	
Q4	The bank does not misuse my personal information	
Q5	I have trust in the banks service	
Q10	My online transactions are always correct	
Q12	I feel my transactions with the banks are safe	
Q13	The banks name is well known and has a good reputation	
Q14	The bank quickly resolves problems I encounter online	
Q6	The website design is attractive	Website Characteristics (Design, content, ease of use)
Q9	It is calm to find what I want on the website	
Q18	Utilizing the bank's website requires no effort.	
Q19	The website structure and information is easy to use	
Q20	The website makes accurate promises about the services rendered	
Q7	The bank replies fast to my demands	Communication (Access, customer support)
Q8	The bank is easily accessed via phone.	
Q15	The site has a customer service representative available online	Efficiency (Speed of site performance)
Q16	It is quick to complete a transaction online	
Q17	Services provides on the bank's website are quick	

4. DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS ANALYSIS (BASED ON THE MODIFIED CONCEPTUAL MODEL)

4.1 Analysis Based on Quality Dimension

The seven-point Likert - type scale can be interpreted as follows: Unsatisfied in one of the following ways: 1; 2; 3; mildly dissatisfied in three cases; 4; neither pleased nor dissatisfied in four. Satisfied but not overly so Number 6 indicates a level of satisfaction, whereas number 7 indicates extreme satisfaction. There are three points on this scale that reflect the tolerance zone: 3, 4, and 5. to put it another way, the participant's service quality level at 3, which is acceptable, but at 5, they get the quality of service which they are looking for. This shows between the number 3 and 5, customers are satisfied with the level of service they receive. For customers at levels 6 and 7, it is more than satisfying that their expectations have been met; they are pleased and extremely pleased with quality of online banking service they receive. Customers at levels 1 and 2 get service quality that falls well short of what they expect (at a suitable level), and as a consequence, they are highly dissatisfied and displeased, respectively. As a required by law quality of service, it's important to point out that it wasn't enough even for providers just satisfy their clients, and as a result, there's a need for further work, such as positive buzz, that would boost the professional image and trustworthiness (Gronroos, 2000). As network operators, banks need to strive to provide great service that exceeds the expectations of their clients, which in this case range from a Likert scale score of 6 to 7. The results of the four servqual dimensions as well as the questionnaires used to describe them will be discussed in the following section.

4.1.1 Service Performance

The first issue that was analysed for this investigation was Question 1, and the median value for that question was 6, which indicates that at least half of the people who participated in this research are satisfied or very satisfied with one aspect of OBS, which is really the ease with which they can access the website. On the Likert Scale, just 3.5 percent of the total of participants gave a score of 3 or lower, indicating that just 3.5 percent of the respondents just weren't pleased or did not receive a sufficient level of service in regard to going just on bank's website promptly. In spite of this, the results show it was not difficult to access the websites of financial institutions.

Item 3 draws emphasis on the fact that the bank's website is available for operation, which indicates that customers are generally pleased with the website; the question has a median value of 6, as well as the value ranges from 1 to 10. Despite this, 24 percent of those who participated in the survey provided responses of 4 or lower on item 3. This suggests that roughly one quarter of the population who responded did not accept the degree of quality of service that they wanted. This suggests that approximately one quarter of OBS users are unable to access the website due to technical difficulties. According to the result of the research, this is an important consideration for OBS because the accessibility of the webpage correlates to its use, and so when incidents happen, these correlations could have a critical effect on customers, leading to dropout as a result of user disillusionment and bad publicity to certain other users.

Pieces 4 and 12 are related to this aspect, and both of them have a median value of 6. This indicates that approximately 505 of the participants answered a score of 6 or 7 on the Likert Scale, so demonstrating that the bank has surpassed the aspirations (requested standard of customer satisfaction) of the OBS users. This can be considered to be of a good grade with regard to this component of the OBS that was given. In addition, it is possible to deduce that not a single respondent has selected a 1 or 2 on the Likert Scale for either of the queries. In response to Question 4, 83.15 percent of customers responded that they were either somewhat satisfied (and well above the expected quality of service) or extremely satisfied with how their private details was handled by the bank. In question 12, respondents gave a score of 90% for the facet of experiencing a sense of safety in financial dealings made with either a bank. These statistics are indeed very high, and then on the Likert Scale, no participants have indicated that they are 1 or 2 on the scale, that also suggests that banking institutions are doing an excellent role of proving the security and anonymity of their consumers' accounts and private details, which is also an essential component for maintaining customers' satisfaction.

Parts 5 and 13 of these dimensions appear to have the same median value with six spotlights as the value. For at least a part of those who responded to the poll, confidence in item 5 of a bank was either very high or very high. They also believed that the banking firm was well-known and had a stellar reputation (Item 13) More than ninety-two percent of individuals polled expressed confidence in the company's image and recognition, however only 89.3% of those polled expressed satisfaction or very satisfaction with their respective banks' item 5 (5 or so on the Likert scale) (Item 13). These are impressive numbers, demonstrating that banks have done a good job of earning the trust of their customers and building a solid brand and reputation of themselves.

Additionally, the median value of 6 in Item 10 suggests that half of those polled are satisfied and/or extremely satisfied with the accuracy of their payment services with bank (Item 10). According to a recent survey, 34.9 percent of respondents polled said they were very satisfied with this part of OBS (7 on the Likert Scale). There are only 9.5 percent who scored 4 or lower on the Likert Scale, which means that only 95% of the people polled did not receive the quality service they were looking for when it came to this component. As a whole, this shows that the bank's OBSQ is dependable and effective.

As a result of the fact that it relates with a serious situation of OBS—namely, the manner in which and the speed with which the bank resolves online concerns for customers—item 14 is extremely difficult to quantify. This established to be an essential component of the service delivery system as that of the manner in which a business resolves issues that are brought up by consumers. This has a significant impact on the customer's overall impression of the service's excellence and whether or not they believe it is being completed efficiently. It has the potential to have a beneficial effect on the growth of relationships between customers, which in turn has the potential to lead to greater confidence levels and happiness among consumers (Gronroos, 2000).

For Item 14, the Likert-type scale indicates that less than half of participants answered 6 or 7 on the Likert-type scale, suggesting low participant satisfaction. This is easy to observe now that 5 has become the new median. In this sample, the OBS participants' goals for this specific component also weren't met to the extent desired. This number can be seen in a variety of ways: In light of the high amount of clients who are dissatisfied with the bank's OBS, as well as my own personal belief in the importance of this particular component of the service, I urge that the bank's management teams give this component of their OBS more attention. There needs to be a greater focus on fixing the internet challenges that clients are having with financial institutions. If you cannot do this, customers may believe that your care was of lower quality. If this happens, client satisfaction may suffer, which could lead to more customers leaving your business (Gronroos, 2000).

Customers are usually happy with the Current Results attained of the OBS that they are using, in addition to being satisfied with the outcome of any troubles that may have arisen. This is demonstrated by the fact that most of the items included in the services quality component have a median value of 6. As can be observed, the majority of questions that relate to the Performance Measurement commitment to improving rank least on discontent (three or less on the Likert Scale) and greatest on respondents' levels of satisfaction (6 or 7 on the Likert Scale). The reality that perhaps the bank customers are highly satisfied with just this aspect of the OBS is demonstrated by this evidence.

4.1.2 Website Characteristics

The look of the bank's website was one of the factors with the lowest median value, as was item no. 6. Only 4 people gave this product a positive review. At least 50 % of the respondents don't care about or are dissatisfied with this OBS feature in some way, form or shape based on this survey results show that 5.9 percent of those polled are dissatisfied. One in four consumers is somewhat dissatisfied with the bank's online design, while one in three customers are neither happy nor dissatisfied. This demonstrates that there is a requirement to investigate this component of the OBS further. Research have already shown that that's really an important factor that impacts the total level of happiness experienced by OBS users, despite the fact that it would be a component that can be simply created as part of the general course of providing service. Additionally, it has been incorporated by a community of scholars into the models that they have developed to investigate the performance quality of internet systems (Jayawardhena, 2000). It is therefore possible to urge that investment bankers do not underestimate the significance of the web pages and instead make adjustments to their web pages in order to make them more appealing to use (Santos, 2003).

There is a median value of five spotlights for both Item 9 and Item 19. As per the Zone of Tolerance, fifty percent of participants have claimed that they have obtained the required quality of the services on these elements of OBS, which is either a five or a higher rating (six or seven on the Likert Scale). On the other hand, it is important to point out that Item 9 has a greater number of responses expressing a minor dissatisfaction (3 on the Likert Scale) and dissatisfaction (2 on the Likert Scale) then Item 19 does. This can be seen by looking at the graphs. 12.4 percent of those who participated in the survey expressed some level of discontent

and disappointment with regard to Item 19 (Graph 12 in Appendix VI). The same opinions were shared by only 7.1% of those who responded to the survey. This demonstrates that a greater number of people are pleased with the organisation and architecture of the information that can be found online (Item 19), as compared to the simplicity with which they may locate what they require online (Item 9). This has shown that even though the substance of the bank's website is well organised and displayed, there will still be a challenging issue in the framework of the webpage overall because some of the customers have troubles quickly finding what they want and on the webpage. This demonstrates that even though the quality of the content is well organised and displayed, there will still be a challenging issue in the configuration of the webpage overall. Users are likely to experience some sense of frustration as a result of this. Therefore, it is essential for investment bankers to examine their website's capabilities and work to make it more user-friendly and straightforward to navigate. In effect, this will lead to an increase in the actual scale of client satisfaction with respect to the performance of OBS.

Question 18's median score of 6 indicates that more than half of those who took the OBS said they were satisfied or extremely satisfied with this part of the study, indicating that their goals were met. As a side note, twenty percent of respondents gave a Likert Scale rating of 4 or below, indicating that they were either uninterested or unsatisfied only with the amount of effort it takes to use the bank's online services. 20% of individuals are not pleased with just this portion of the online; so, there is a need for the companies to make their webs simpler and more user-friendly in order to make them more accessible.

When Item 20 has a median score of 5, it means that at least half of those who took the survey believe they received the level of service they expected, or even a level higher (6 or 7 on the Likert Scale). Respondents who gave a Likert Scale rating of 4 or below indicated that they had not received the level of service they had hoped for when it came to their bank's ability to keep its promises. Although 24.2 percent of OBS customers appear to have received an adequate level of service, it should be noted that this is a large percentage for OBS customers who are not pleased with the bank's claims. This is something that should be given some serious consideration.

4.1.3 Communication

Working with where the bank reacts to the demands of customers (Item 7), and the ease, in which the bank may be reached through telephones when there's no need (Item 8), are both sensitive components of service quality that are thought crucial in the performance of goods. The objects have the potential to play a very significant part in the service delivery recovery process, and then if properly implemented, they have the potential to even have a positive effect on the overall user satisfaction, which results from improved developing relationships as well as the consolidation of trust (Gronroos, 2000). That question had the most unanswered responses of all of them (15 of 170 at 8.82 percent for Q7 and 7 of 170 at 4.12 percent for Q8). Responders are still expected to have no prior experience with the aforementioned aspects of service, but this shows that some responders have such skill. The amount of satisfaction that the participants have with regard to this aspect is quite low. Both Item 7 and Item 8 have median values of 4, with Item 7 being slightly lower than Item 8. It can be deduced from this that more

than half of the respondents encountered difficulties in obtaining immediate answers to their inquiries from either the bank (Item 7), and that fewer than half of the respondents were able to contact the bank by cellular phone without encountering any problems whenever the occasion demanded it (Item 8). When looking at statistics, sixty percent of participants gave a score of four or lower for Item 7, and thirty-two and a half percent gave a score of four or lower for Item 8. These are the responders their expectations when it comes these facets of OBS really aren't reached to the level of achievement that is intended.

Due to the fact that these numbers are the greatest seen to date, it is crucial that prompt corrective actions be made in order to repair these aspects of the OBS in order to enhance the service level of healthcare that is offered. It is recommended that the management of the bank offer additional emphasis to these considerations that affect the relatively large percentage of clients who are dissatisfied with the services they receive. According to the findings of the study, this needs to be done as soon as possible because improper and ineffective interaction with the bank can result in questions and concerns faced by customers not even being answered immediately and adequately, which in turn leads to a growth in the number of people complaining. Because of this, the consumers may feel as though they are obligated to provide good service, which could ultimately lead towards retention (Gronroos, 2000). Customers are looking for a service supplier who can provide a complete and prompt response to any difficulties they may have.

4.1.4 Efficiency

When talking to Item 16, the median number to begin with is 6, which indicates that in at least fifty percent of those surveyed have responded that they should be satisfied or very satisfied with this aspect of OBS but also that their aspirations have been surpassed. On the Likert Scale, just 11.2% of respondents gave a score of 4 or lower, which indicates that only 11.2% of participants are either unsatisfied or disinterested about the length of time it takes to finish a business on the bank's website (Item 16). This demonstrates that the clients are, on the whole, satisfied only with time it takes to finish a business over the internet, and one can say that this endeavour was successful because it contributes to measuring the efficacy of the OBS that was supplied. These can be observed in the chart that reveals that 65.3% of participants have claimed that they are content with the OBS element, or that they must be extremely satisfied with this now.

Item 17 has a median value of 5, which indicates that at least percent of the participants obtained the performance of internet delivering services that they expected or even quicker speeds. This can be inferred from the fact that the median value is 5. 46.1% of participants have indicated that they are content or very satisfied with both the pace of OBS delivery, while 20.4% have indicated that they are not satisfied with the pace, scoring a 4 or below on the Likert Scale. This percentage is greater than the percentage for Item 16, which was 25%. This demonstrates that although customers are usually pleased with the pace at which their transactions are processed, there is still a problem with both the average speed of delivery of services, which is when it has to be addressed. As a result, bank management need to conduct an analysis of the online services and service process in order to identify the source of the

problem and search for long-term remedies. Regular and regular evaluation of all the same can also be of assistance to management team to ensure overall productivity improvements.

4.1.5 Satisfaction and Dissatisfaction Levels of Customers on Different Quality Dimensions

The next step of the research involved determining the proportion of participants who gave responses of 6 or 7 on the Likert Scale, including the number of people who gave responses of 3 below than on the scale, and the proportion of people who gave responses of 6 and 7 with each of the quality attributes in the model. After tallying up all of the proportions of the things that belonged to a particular strength component, the final tally was arrived at by multiplying the grand total by the data set and then dividing. At this stage, it was presumed that each item had almost the same level of significance in relation to the aspect in question.

This was done with the intention of demonstrating the degree to which the participants were satisfied for each of the elements as well as several other aspects. This, in turn, puts the spotlight on the components of the bank's automated website that would need to be concentrated on owing to poor client satisfaction for the benefit of an organization as well as the features that were already normally expected by the majority respondents.

Table 5 below shows the figures to be used in the analysis that follows

Table 5: the Percentages for the Dimensions for the Respondents that have Stated 4 or below, 3 or below and 6 or 7 on the Lickert Scale

Respondents who have stated 4 or below on the Lickert Scale		Respondents who have stated 3 or below on the Lickert Scale		Respondents who have stated 6 or 7 below on the Lickert Scale	
Dimension	% of total respondents	Dimension	% of total respondents	Dimension	% of total respondents
Service Performance	15.7625	Service Performance	2.8375	Communication	31.8
Efficiency	15.8	Efficiency	3.85	Website Characteristics	40.4
Website Characteristics	29.84	Website Characteristics	9.68	Efficiency	55.7
Communication	46.25	Communication	12.3	Service Performance	61.475

*The figures are captured in ascending order

Attendees who said they had been dissatisfied as well as received the minimum adequate standard of customer satisfaction and service quality (OBSQ) were guesstimated to use the Likert Scale statistics for those who said they have been dissatisfied or received the least acceptable level of customer satisfaction and service quality (OBSQ). Results were analysed using the Likert Scale, which measures satisfaction with an online banking experience. On the other hand, it indicates individuals whose dreams came true on the average (nor satisfied nor dissatisfied). With a score of 60 percent, participants indicated that they were either dissatisfied as well as indifferent with following OBS factors: The timely response of the bank to clients' queries (Item 7), the layout of bank website (Item 6), the fast solution of clients' troubles (Item 14), and ease in which customers could really reach the commercial bank via phone (Item 8). In order to best satisfy its customers, the bank must pay more attention to these sections of the OBS, which have relatively high numbers, to increase consumer satisfaction with the services

they provide. The facets of the OBS where the least amount survey participants have already shown dissatisfaction or disinterest are including: having a well-known professional reputation (Item 13) with a score of 7.1 percent; accuracy of online purchases managed to carry out (Item 10) with a score of 9.55; experiencing a sense of safety when conducting transaction records with the bank (Item 12) with a score of 10 percent; and having confidence in the bank (Item 5) with a score of 10.7 percent. This demonstrates that the portion of respondents who are dissatisfied or indifferent with the Services Quality dimension is at 15.76255, while the proportion that is dissatisfied or indifferent with the economy dimension is at 15.8 percent. Interaction, which had a score of 46.25 percent, and Website Attributes, which received a score of 29.84 percent, are the quality categories with the highest levels of considerable indifferent among participants. On the Likert Scale, a score of 3 or lower indicates that a participant is dissatisfied but rather that they obtain the basic minimum quality of services that they are prepared to accept. On the other hand, a score of 6 or 7 indicates that a participant is satisfied but also that their preconceptions have been surpassed. On the Likert scale, a score of three or below indicates dissatisfaction or a lowest amount of appropriate service quality; respondents with scores in this range may require prompt assistance to ensure that the resulting service quality doesn't really continue to deteriorate.

The majority of people whose preconceptions of the OBS have been surpassed and who are therefore satisfied can be estimated based on the number of survey participants who asserted either 6 or 7. This information can be used to infer the degree to whom the bank has been successful as a service provider in providing customers with high-quality products and services in relation to the OBS. When looking at the numbers, it can be seen that the fewest number of participants have given a rating of 6 or 7 for the following components: the layout of the webpage (Item 6) with 15.9 percent, timely response first from financial institution to customers' queries (Item 7) with 19.4 percent, quick solutions to customers' troubles (Item 14) with 38.1 percent, and easiness of discovering what is required upon that website (Item 9) with 38.5 percent. On the other hand, the majority of participants have indicated a higher level of satisfaction (a score of 6 or 7 on the scale) with facets such as the bank having a well-known identity and a strong reputation (Item 13) with a percentage of 74.7 percent, the accuracy of online transactions (Item 10) with a percentage of 71 percent, a sense of safety when conducting transaction records with the bank (Item 12) with a percentage of 70 percent, and indeed the non-misuse of personally identifiable information. Estimates suggest that 61.475 percent of consumers are satisfied with Quality Service, while 55.7 percent of participants are satisfied with Communication and 40.4% are satisfied with Web page Characteristics, while only 312.8 percent of customers are satisfied with Quality Service. Only 1.2 percent of those who took the survey and gave it a Likert scale score of 3 or decrease said they were dissatisfied with the bank's well-known name and reputation (Item 20), only 1.8 percent said they were dissatisfied with the precision of online purchases (Item 10), and only 1% said they felt safe doing business with the bank. Respondents expressed dissatisfaction with the following elements: the design of said webpage (Item 6), with a proportion of 21.8 percent; the response promptly from the bank to clients' queries (Item 7), with a percentage of 14.2 percent; the ease of discovering what is required here on webpage (Item 9), with a percentage of 12.4 percent; and the easiness

of reaching the bank through the use of telephone (Item 10) (all with a percentage of 12.4 percent). When it comes to service performance (2.8375 basis points) and efficiency (3.85%), the estimated percentages reveal that fewer people were dissatisfied or received service that fell short of minimum norms of perceived quality. Most participants expressed discontent or obtained a low degree of perceived service quality for Communication at 12.3% and web page Personality traits at 9.68%. As a result, it's apparent that investment bankers need to pay special attention to the service quality dimensions of Interactions and Website Qualities.

More than 60% of consumers are happy with service performance, 57% are happy with interaction and 40% of participants are happy with web page characteristics, according to our estimates. Recently, the proportions of customers who are satisfied with Service Efficiency & Achievement have increased. In the OBS areas of well-known financial numbers and reliability (1.2 percent), precision in online transactions (1.8 percent), and feeling comfortable in bank transactions (2.4 percent), there are fewer persons who have expressed dissatisfaction or attained a minimum level of service quality. Most participants expressed dissatisfaction or even a basic minimum level of quality of service again for following aspects: 10.4 percent of those surveyed answered "yes" to this question (Item 8). Survey participants were less likely to express dissatisfaction or receive minimum requirements for perception of service quality in regards to Service performance (2.8375 percent) and Efficiency (3.85 percent), but a greater proportion of them did so in regards to ethical servqual model limits for Provider performance and Efficiency (the two most important factors) (9.68 percent). As a result, bank executives should focus their efforts on improving customer interaction and the functionality of their websites.

Estimates show that 61.475 percent of customers are satisfied with Service Performance, while 55.7 percent of participants are satisfied with Interaction and 40.4 percent are satisfied with Web page Characteristics. The proportions that show the most clients have shown higher levels of satisfaction with Provider Performance and Effectiveness just recently. If you look at people surveyed who gave a Likert scale rating below 3, you'll find that fewer people have expressed discontent or obtained a least level of service quality for the following OBS areas: well-known financial figures and reliability at 1.2 percent; precision in online transactions at 1.8 percent; and feeling confident in bank transactions at 2.4 percent. While the majority of respondents expressed dissatisfaction with the website's architecture (Item 6; 21.8 percent of survey participants), the prompt response from the financial institution to customers' requests (Item 7; 14.2 percent of respondents), the ease with which customers can find what they need on the website (Item 9; 12.4 % of survey participants), and the ease with which customers can contact the bank (Item 10; 10.4 percent of respondents) (Item 8; 10.4 percent of respondents). A lower percentage of participants in the survey expressed dissatisfaction as well as received a minimum standard of acceptable quality service (2.8375 percent) and efficiency (3.85 percent) in relation to the servqual model, but the percentage of participants who expressed dissatisfaction as well as received a minimal standard of acceptable service performance (community engagement) (2.8375 percent) was higher (9.68 percent). This suggests that communication & website features are the quality areas that administrators of financial institutions should pay the most attention to.

5. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

201 people participated in the survey for this study, but only 170 of them ended up using for the research. Cronbach's Alpha Test of Reliability and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) were carried out in order to analyse the data and determine the degree to which it could be trusted. The results of the Cronbach's Alpha Test of Reliability revealed that the parameters that were utilized in the model had a satisfactory degree of stability. Performing PCA resulted in several modifications being made to the conceptual model, including the reduction of the initial dimensionality to four and the removal of three components from the questionnaire survey (Question2, Question11, and Question15).

One scale that contained all four aspects was used in the study's finalized version of the model that was designed for measuring OBSQ. And those are the service quality characteristics that, according to the study that was carried out, the banks must take into consideration when conducting an evaluation of their OBS. In addition to this, there are seventeen different components that are employed to define those measurements. It is possible for the banks to use the items that have been described in order to assess the OBSQ in accordance with the characteristics that have been offered in the study. Following the modification of the theoretical model, research study measured the descriptive statistics information that was supplied in the research in order to determine how consumers regarded the various facets of the OBS that they made use of. The study also aims to determine the customers' satisfaction by the excellence related dimensions that relate to the altered theory building in order to come to a conclusion regarding the facets of OBS that needs to be improved and awareness in particular with respect to the management teams of the banks.

As a result of the large investments that banks have made and continue to make into the online component, customer satisfaction are rapidly now one of the most important criteria in influencing the competitiveness of online banking services (OBS). Establishing and maintaining long-term client relationships is necessary in order to generate good customer value through the use of the internet (Parasuraman A. Z., 2005). Providing services of a high level is amongst the most fundamental strategies to achieve high levels of customer satisfaction and, as a result, win the loyalty of customers. To this end, it is seen why it is considered significant for banks to be capable of measuring and assess the efficacy of the OBS in order to take appropriate action to correct characteristics of their OBS that consumers experience unsatisfying, preserve those that they would be satisfied with, and keep improving those that they're not even satisfied to. In this way, it is seen how being possible to quantify and assess the quality of the OBS is considered important for banks.

Following previous research, an updated version of a model developed by Parasuraman A. B., (1991) was used to evaluate the quality of service in the financial sector, and a conceptual framework was developed that could also be used to evaluate OBSQ (Parasuraman A. B., 1991). In addition to this, the research analyzed the degrees of consumer contentment with the many facets of OBS that they made use of, basing its findings on a theoretical model that had previously been used and subsequently updated.

The majority of participants have expressed dissatisfaction or disinterest regarding the following facets: the bank's immediate answers to the customer's queries, the easy fixes to the customer's troubles, the layout of the bank's website, the ease with which the consumer can reach the bank via telephone, as well as the ease with which the consumer can find whatever the client requirements on the webpage. It is also possible to draw the conclusion that banks this seems to operate very well on the customer desired performance aspects of OBS. This is because these characteristics scored top on the participants' levels of satisfaction. It was also shown that the features of communications and websites constantly placed top on discontent, and as a result, the bank management had to take this into consideration when devising strategies for intervention and redress. In the course of our observations, one thing that stuck out was the fact that the components of the OBS that score higher in discontent, such as the Website Characteristics dimensions, are more Internet sites specific. When it comes to overall internet platform quality, banks may not place as much importance on this feature as they do on other aspects of their services. OBS sees this site as the "truth assassin" between customers and their institutions since of the absence of face-to-face communication that can be made in a digital context. At all times, it is important to remember this. There must be a sense of coherence between the website and the overall excellence hard work of the service provider. Finally, a better-quality website is a crucial part of the OBS accessible.

Based on a model developed by Parasuraman for evaluating the effectiveness for online services, this study developed an approach for analyzing the quality the OBS (2002). Researchers discovered that in command to attain advanced levels of dependability and constancy, the initial project model needed to be modified. As a result, a fundamental notion was developed, one that will benefit from further testing and refinement based on the results of surveys conducted with a larger population of participants from other organizations. When time and resources were limited in the study that had to be done because of time and resources, a reduced number of quality measurements and items have been used in the research method. This was done to make participation in the survey easier and more convenient. It is important to note, as a final point of discussion, that although the established device can then be used to start measuring the customer satisfaction level with diverse components of OBS, does not demonstrate the comparative merits of any of areas in relative towards the additional quality of service. It would be intriguing to quantify that include these facets in future investigations as well.

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